

From Lick the Toad to Craft the Code

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ABSTRACT

As in the era of Ars Nova which provided the platform for composers' exploration of rhythmical representation, (mobile) technology-mediated audience participation is now baby booming due to the rapid discourse of the web-based technologies open to any layman who is interested in the field of innovative music-making. Expanding on the main focus of this paper, that is, technology mediated audience interaction during live coding, networked capabilities in music systems can provide the means for realizing projects that empower audience interaction in live coding performances. Lick the Toad is a custom-made system developed using web technologies and it was built to provide a platform for interaction between members of the audience and performer(s) enabling an ongoing dialogue between individual sound nodes generated by users' devices and live coders as a means to govern the decisions of the coding procedure. To enhance variability of sonic events amongst the users the system uses a neural network model trained using input generated by the users. This is a ready-to-use sound-making interface that can generate sound out of the box while engaging in a bidirectional communication using Open Sound Control (OSC) messages that are shared to an accompanying live coding interface environment built in SuperCollider for this purpose. A demonstration of the project and its creative outputs are provided in the paper as well as an analysis of a musical performance which was created using this system.

1. INTRODUCTION

Much of practice-based research has highlighted live coding's contribution to the ethos of liveness in music performance, using improvisation as the impetus for real-time exploration under the rubric of live and improvised electronic music. Live coding seems to be the ultimate medium to release one from previous decisions that are implemented in a performance system prior to the time of the performance (Blackwell et al. 2022, 159-160). However, much of this exploration focuses on a traditional performer-audience dichotomy, leaving the audience outside the creative equation. LTT has taken many spins since its original conception (Vasilakos 2022, 2021), of these the aim to enable collaborative participation of the audience during a live coding performance and allowing users to interact with each other at the same time is the primary focus of this paper.

Recent advances in networking communication have expanded in music and sound interaction. Various showcases and projects have provided with ample proof that mobile devices can be proven as handy tools to establish real time interactions in the context of real time sonification¹ (Hermann, Hunt, and Neuhoff 2011) running lightweight applications (Bevilacqua et al. 2021; Xambó and Roma 2020; Hödl et al. 2020). However, in the field of live coding, the idea of allowing the audience to have dynamic communication during performance remains underdeveloped and therefore provides an opportunity for improvement and artistic exploration. Data sharing, arguably, helps to establish real-time communication to influence the decisions and directions which are taken on the fly.

Therefore, the conceptual foundations of this study rest upon the rich history of utilizing networks for artistic exploration in electronic music.

From early pioneers like Thaddeus Cahill and Telharmonium (Manning 2004) to contemporary practices like The Hub (Gresham-Lancaster, 1998) and current approaches of live coding ensembles such as, the

¹ Sonification is the practice of rendering inaudible data to sound.

PowerBooks_Unplugged (Rohrhuber et al. 2007), the Cybernetic Orchestra (Ogborn 2014) and the Birmingham Ensemble for Electroacoustic Research (Wilson et al. 2014), networks have served as a medium for decentralized sonic expression and real-time communication. By employing platforms such as SuperCollider and leveraging Open Sound Control (OSC) communication, this project seeks to expand upon this tradition offering a versatile tool for experimentation in sound synthesis contexts.

Central to this endeavour is the aim to engage audiences actively during live coding performances, shifting them from passive listeners to active participants in the compositional process. By utilizing web technologies and networked capabilities, it enables an ongoing dialogue where individual sound nodes generated by users' devices interact with live coders to influence the coding procedure. This approach not only opens new avenues for live music-making but also presents novel challenges, particularly in integrating neural network capabilities into the realm of live coding improvisation and networking technologies. By exploring these interactions, this system aims to advance our understanding of networked music systems and their potential for collaborative artistic expression. To justify the feasibility of the project a live performance was recorded for this purpose and is presented at the end of this paper. Some videos that showcase the system in realistic scenarios are also provided in this playlist².

2. BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION

The primary motivation behind this project originated from the concept of involving audience members in live coding sessions. The aim was to enhance the experience for the audience and make live coding more accessible. Live coding can sometimes appear esoteric, where the coder demonstrates their programming prowess in isolation. By encouraging audience participation and interference, the project sought to break down barriers, engage viewers more deeply, and make the process of live coding a collaborative and inclusive experience.

LTT aims to explore a step further beyond the display of the coder's action akin to solve the issue of esotericism and allow the audience play a pivotal role during improvisation. In turn this may have a twofold impact, assigning data to the coder for further elaboration of common grounds, and at the same transcend the source of sound from the performer's computer to other members of the audience. This may provide further cues or directions and form a sonic map to navigate wherein adjusting to the responds and spontaneity of the audience's sonic upheavals.

Other projects which investigate audience participation is Diego Dorado's "live coding with emojis project", a performance of this project can be found at this link³. The method which was followed in his project allows members of the audience insert emojis in TidalCycles (<https://tidalcycles.org/>) patterns and effectively associating visual connections of various emojis with sounds, e.g., a kick-drum sound with flexed biceps emoji or clap sounds with clap emojis and so on.

3. LTT: DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

LTT facilitates client access via the hosting computer's IP address followed by the '/client' string, as illustrated in Figure 1. Users are represented as virtual points with each user capable of manipulating their respective point's position along the X and Y axes. This movement is visualized by everyone and enables interaction with other users. The connectivity and interaction among nodes are depicted in Figure 1, wherein users become interconnected when in proximity to one another.

Upon user interaction, the system transmits the X and Y coordinates of the node on the screen to the server, which serves as input data for training purposes. The output value is determined by the user's selection of a targeting value assigning it as low, mid, and high. These correspond to frequency value 80,

² <https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLiCZTYIqSUAaOKWKS9R0jorUrvKvdkKFI>

³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OwKUuypxP6Y&t=112s>

220, 660 respectively. Thus, the system is trained based on the input values associated with the X and Y movements of the user's node on the screen. By associating this input (xs) with the targeting value (freq) the prediction is generating a regression value between each targeting values. Therefore, each output value is essentially a target value linked to the user's X and Y input allocation obtained during interaction with the system.

Data collection is manually initiated from the "main" interface, detailed in the subsequent section. Users can transition to the main interface to collect new data, which can be stored, downloaded, and placed in the application folder for future utilization without necessitating additional data collection. A snippet of the data is presented below:

```
{"data": [{"xs": {"x": 847.3772513163357, "y": 350.7443843153129}, "ys": {"freq": 660}}, {"xs": {"x": 979.0927893896481, "y": 532.9821317771332}, "ys": {"freq": 120}}, {"xs": {"x": 883.9268992201362, "y": 736.4900062742083}, "ys": {"freq": 120}}, {"xs": {"x": 49.12928631795192, "y": 58.166059380152966}, "ys": {"freq": 120}}, {"xs": {"x": 623.6468465406239, "y": 466.9990679157592}, "ys": {"freq": 80}}, {"xs": {"x": 953.8540803551017, "y": 526.022703267118}, "ys": {"freq": 660}}, {"xs": {"x": 979.0927893896481, "y": 532.9821317771332}, "ys": {"freq": 120}}]}
```


Figure 1. User interaction and generation of training data in LTT.

4. IMPLEMENTATION DETAILS

LTT is accessible on both laptops and mobile devices such as smartphones and tablets. The platform offers two primary functionalities: data generation and acquisition/training mode. Users can access these functionalities by entering specific URLs in their browser, preceded by the IP address of the server, as detailed in the preceding section. Upon completing data acquisition and initiating training, the application is in prediction mode, providing visualizations of prediction values and participant count.

The interface is implemented using JavaScript and its runtime environment NodeJS, leveraging P5JS and VUE framework. It uses Web Sockets to offer real time visualization of users and respective data

broadcasting. It also supports client and server OSC communication via Web Sockets using OSC.JS (<https://github.com/colinbdclark/osc.js/>). Furthermore, sound generation is implemented using Tone.JS library (<https://tonejs.github.io/>). A built-in neural network is implemented using the ML5.JS library (<https://ml5js.org/>).

5. DESIGN AND FEATURES

While the interface operates independently on each user's device, enabling training and predictions generated by the neural network model, it also fosters communication among users, enhancing collective synergy. To emphasize this feature, the tempo is dynamically associated with the number of users. The tempo within the system is dynamically adjusted relative to the number of users. Initially set at a fixed rate of 120 beats per minute (bpm), this tempo can be easily modified to accommodate slower or faster rhythm patterns for each node. For a visual representation of the current state of the interface, please see the figure below.

Figure 2. Main Interface of LTT: operations and functionalities for user interaction.

Users have the capability to interact with the application and generate prediction values either manually or automatically. As of the current writing, manual prediction is feasible through the web browser console within a desktop environment after opening the developer view page while in browser. Conversely, automatic prediction employs a Perlin noise generator to simulate user selection of X and Y points for on-screen prediction randomly within the selection field, as illustrated in Figure 2 (tags: training data points, real time prediction output). In both scenarios, users determine when to update the Markov states with new data, subtracting the current prediction position from the regression value (Figure 2, frequency value).

Thus, the interactive aspect of the neural network's and sound and data transmission is based on the current prediction value, which subsequently modifies the Markov chain states, introducing another layer

of randomness based on the regression value corresponding to the frequency of the generated pattern by the embedded synthesizer. During live coding interactions, users transmit these pattern data as OSC messages, with the live coder dynamically and mapping them in real-time, fostering further auditory connections. The coder is able to selectively engage with specific users creating interaction links while others continue transmitting data simultaneously. User ID is assigned as a long string with arbitrary letters e.g., “40ZtF8hXWdMouqrUAABL” as shown in figures 2 and 3.

Consequently, the user experience can be likened to a spotlight experience within the audience, as the connection of their sounds with the coder's responses establishing a sense of reciprocal engagement, driving involvement and jointly shaping the performance's trajectory. In this egalitarian framework of involvement, the coder may seamlessly blend data from multiple users to control synthesizer parameters while live coding. For instance, merging data streams from two users to manipulate the pitch parameter of a pattern in SuperCollider (see Section 6.1).

To underscore the system's interactive attributes and gauge its feasibility, a video was produced showcasing its capabilities in real-world settings. To provide a deeper understanding of audience interaction, a system demonstration involving both desktop computers and mobile devices was recorded and can be accessed at the provided link⁴. Additionally, a survey was conducted to gather feedback, informing further development and enhancement efforts. Verbatim comments from participants are provided at table 2 after the conclusion of this paper and will be grown by the time of presenting the paper.

5.1 Interface Commands

The table below provides an explanation of the available commands to allow the user run basic tasks such as, saving the data file locally or starting the training process, etc. The commands are triggered by a key on the keyboard of the computer or accessed from the smartphone/tablet touchscreen.

Key	Controls
C	Collection of data
D	Starts training with stored data
S	Save locally training/collected data
P	Save a screenshot of prediction values
T	Start training with newly collected data
F	Fetches data for training from GitHub (not working yet)
M	Save model
N	Switch to manual prediction or vice versa

Table 1. LTT commands associated with keys to trigger implemented functions.

For further information about technical details can be found in the GitHub repository of the project at this link⁵.

6. LIVE CODING IN SUPERCOLLIDER

All live coding components and resources for handling and operating on the incoming messages are developed in the SuperCollider language. These are newly developed and propose a primer approach on parsing and utilizing the data at hand combining Just in time library (JITlib) and other utilities provided

⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLiCZTYIqSUAaOKWks9R0jorUrvKvdkKFI>

⁵ <https://github.com/KonVas/lick-the-toad>

by the language. The system is an open-source project and capable with other data following the appropriate format. Data in SC is accessed individually from each user based on their ID that is assigned by the server the moment of opening the interface on their browser. The data is allocated in a dictionary (*~dict*) using the ID string (*/id_string*). The following code snippet shows the parsing of the incoming OSC data streams and their allocation in the dictionary. These are sorted according to their ID as follows. A pop up window allows the user selection and fetching of their current data embedded in a Pbind and Pdef alike. The benefits of this approach is that it can be edited and executed inside the window and elaborated on the interactivity relationship between the coder and incoming data thoroughly in the next section.

```
[ /wfiRwJaZy3wktE2MAAAX, {"0": "455.00", "1": "211.00", "2": "455.00"}]; //dummy OSC message.
```

```
~dict = ();
```

```
OSCdef(\lickin, { |...args|
  var userID = args[0][1].asString.asSymbol;
  var keys_2_symbols = { |v, i| (i % 2 == 0).if(v.asSymbol, v)};
  var oscArray = args[0][2].asString.parseJSON.asPairs.collect(keys_2_symbols).asEvent;
  var checkBadVals = oscArray.collect(_.notNil).reject(_.isNil) != false;
  var time = args[1];
  if(checkBadVals) {
    //"User with ID: % sent message % at time %\n".postf(userID, oscArray, args[1]);
    ~dict[userID] = oscArray;
    oscArray.keysValuesDo({ |index, value|
      {
        \notifier.changed(~keyIndex[index.interpretVal], userID, value.interpretVal, time)
      }.defer;
    });
  };
}, '/lick');
```

6.1 From toads to *crafting codes*

In addition to the dictionary implementation and rendering into events (key/value pairs) described later, a first stage to monitor the incoming data is implemented involving a window with sliders that are modulated by the incoming values. Using a notification system found at this link⁶ it helps to control other elements in the program e.g., a GUI as a way to monitoring the communication live. While this is the first stage of parsing the incoming OSC from all users in SuperCollider, a more tailored interface was required in order to enhance the live coding process and *mould* the incoming values as raw material as is currently the main focus of this project. A function that is able to parse the data and render into events in SC automagically besides requiring to hardcoding event streams during the coding process is embedded in the system. Using Pbinds to wrap the patterns the system offers a ready to use performance mechanism, which allows to map the incoming values to dedicated *synthdefs* while live coding. This is following a simple, yet efficient solution of a text window from where the user may execute the Pbind(s) at their will (see fig. 3) or copy and modify them further. This approach was selected due to its openness and non-deterministic way to map values to parameters of synthesizers in real time. While this is a simple approach it allows one to implement a wide range of mapping configurations between the incoming data and the streaming values to the synthesis modules at hand. While the window allows the selection of each user individually it helps to associate them with Pbinds separately, and thus offering a handy method to entangle code from each toad on the fly.

⁶ <https://github.com/iani/SC?tab=readme-ov-file#systemextensions>

Figure 3. An overview of LTT and custom system for receiving and rendering data in SuperCollider.

The Pbind can be wrapped in a Pdef, a class of JITLib which allows to intervene while the streams are playing without interrupting the sound. These are generated inside the text window named Capture Patterns after pressing the generate button. This performance approach was adopted because it offers a universal way to interact with SuperCollider's dynamic programming techniques at the same time making it accessible to live coders.

```
Pdef(\userID##, Pbind(\dur, 0.1, \instrument, \mysynth,
  \degree, Pseq([ 5.34, 6.54, 6.54, 5.34, 5.34, 6.54, 5.34, 6.54 ] /3,
  inf);
```

On the side of accessibility, the Pbinds are formed following generic event keys, such as degree, octave etc. Assuming a synthdef has a frequency argument value conversion in SuperCollider helps to map universal parameters such as *degree* synthesisers with no extra modification (see next code example) in order to make it easy to interact.

The amount of the stream players and their mappings are only descriptive. The amount of complexity that is one is able to achieve by trial and error between associations of incoming values embedded in patterns to control parameters of sound is a far from the need for single definition or single approach. This, however, poses an interesting question of optimisation of parameter mapping in LTT and an area for improvement for the live coding process, which will be explored in future directions of the system after acquiring enough knowledge performing with the system.

```
SynthDef.new(\mysynth, {
  arg freq = 120.0, amp = 0.5, out = 0;
```

```
var signal, filter, env;  
env = EnvGen.kr(Env.perc(0.1, 2.0), doneAction: 2);  
signal = SinOsc.ar(freq: freq, phase: pi*1.0.rand, mul: env);  
signal = signal * 0.5;  
Out.ar(out, signal);  
}).add;
```

7. IMPACT ON MUSICING & LIVE CODING

To present the capabilities of LTT a video was recorded to demonstrate the system using various live coding techniques that were described formerly. The video can be found at this link⁷, and a description of the video highlighting the approaches that was followed are outlined as follows. Users are emulated using two separate browser tabs run in the computer that is also running the server. Interacting with streams and values is the basis for interacting with the sonic outcomes of the user's devices and establishing an impromptu soundscape comprising virtual members of the audience and a live coding performance. The clients are also controlled from SuperCollider, using bidirectional OSC communication. Two commands were implemented: triggering the running clients to send new data, and also play the notes simultaneously. As already touched in the previous section the number of the stream players which can be generated are unlimited. This offers an enormous amount of layering of sounds while performing when analysing the system in music/sound terms. The streams of the events triggering new sound nodes in SuperCollider are creating a complex sound scape which is comprised by the juxtaposition of individual evolving sounds, forming a unified result mapping variations of similar notes yet interpreted in multiple ways. The performance is approached in playing with different layers at the same time modifying their parameters in time or in a post-production level or altering the sound using effect processors such as, pitch shifters, delays, and equalizers and whatnot. The sound outcome that is generated is characterized by the polyrhythmic complexity to drown sounds. The improvisation element in LTT is therefore suggested to perform following a specific approach, however, the amount of interpretation of the generated data and their mappings leave an enormous space to the performer for real time exploration. That is to say, that while limitations can be sometimes narrowing down the possibilities, they also provide a pathway to let one unfold their imagination and helping to form the decisions that are taken during live coding by listening the audience's sounds. While audience members and coder(s) are bound to this pact of interaction the amount of freedom of both ends yields creating various sonic interactions, from rhythmical to evolving sound nodes effectively shaping the overall musical outcome in a collective and coherent manner.

8. FUTURE DIRECTIONS

The functionality of interconnected users represents an area for further exploration in future iterations of the interface. This feature could enable the system to transmit data only when the proximity of one user overlaps with that of others within the network. By incorporating such functionality, the system could optimize data exchange and interaction among users by focusing on those within close proximity, potentially enhancing the overall user experience and facilitating more meaningful connections between participants. This aspect will be a focal point for future development, with the aim of refining and implementing this feature to enrich the collaborative aspects of the interface.

9. CONCLUSION

LTT is an interactive web-based application which was built to enable the real time communication between audience members and live coding performers. Using LTT allows to establish an ongoing dialogue between audiences and coders influencing the decisions of the coding process, and affording the audience to actively participate in the performance instead of observing the live coding process passively.

⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLiCZTYIqSUAaOKWks9R0jorUrvKvdkKFI>

Using Socket programming for user interaction it provides a lightweight toolkit for networking and accessibility and at the same time it allows users to form their ad-hoc soundscapes. It requires no prior knowledge in sound synthesis making it an attractive tool for collective sonification. Following the necessary tweaks in the source code, it may adapt to other forms of data in order to be used for other projects and used as a primer for technology mediated audience interaction in live coding. The live coding system affords the easy adaptation of real time generated event players, which can be associated with running synthesizers following the standard techniques of SuperCollider making it less esoteric performance system for the general community of live coding familiar with SuperCollider. Live coding performances with LTT entail a micro level management of pattern-based manipulations which help to create complex rhythmical structures and textural sounds that are tangled with the soundscape that is dynamically shaped by the audience affording both participants and performers to construct an ongoing dialogue during live coding performances and contribute on the accessibility to the general public.

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Annex

Timestamp	Is the interface accessible for someone that has never used it before?	Was the interface requiring information that need to be demonstrated first?	Is the system engaging terms of usability	Is the system engaging terms of sound design	What can be improved based on your experience (e.g., interaction buttons, sound design ability, machine learning visuals, information about the project etc.)
2024/03/14 1:51:52 pm GMT+8	Easy	No it was straight forward what I can do	10	Interesting	More information about the project can be provided
2024/03/14 3:32:03 pm GMT+8	Relatively easy	Needs some explanation first	8	Interesting	More buttons for interaction with sounds might be added to increase the feeling of involvement.
2024/03/14 4:49:56 pm GMT+8	Easy	No it was straight forward what I can do	9	Interesting	The internet speed has a significant impact on the results

Table 2. Users' comments after interacting and performing with LTT.

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